

HR TECHNIQUES USED BY NOKIA IN THE WORLD OF GLOBALISATION

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Abstract:-

Mobile phone ownership in India is growing rapidly, six million new mobile subscriptions are added each month and one in five Indian's will own a phone by the end of the year. Eli Sundback, Executive vice president ,corporate relations and responsibility, at Nokia, said Mobile phone ownership in India is growing at a phenomenal pace. This new found mobility undoubtedly has the potential to make a major contribution to socioeconomic development and we recognize the responsibility we have to play a key role in achieving .This has been doing in developing market like India for several years to understand how we can deliver on our goal of making universal access to technology and the associated benefits a reality.

Dr.Aditya dev sood ,the report highlights how many new adopters of mobile phones have found their income rise, he explained these findings as the increased production made possible through mobile communications. While mobile phones are widely a communication medium, they should really be seen as a new and essential form of infrastructure that will transform a host of other services sector in rural economies around the world.

According to industry analysts, by 2010, the mobile phones industry in India will be driven by voice, multimedia and mobile services for organizations. The teledensity in India was estimated to increase to 18% by mobile subscription rising to 148.77 million by that time. In many instances the cell phone has become the only basic telephone link of a household enterprises India, rather than a landline phone. It was turning out to be more economical and

efficient that fixed line telephones. So there was great scope for further expansion with reduction in the cost of ownership..

Key words:-

CDMA-Code Divisional Multiple Asscess , GSM- Global Sim Moduel ,WAP- Wireless protocol which is used as for internet ,GPRS- general packet radio service ,HRA- human resource management ,MKT- Marketing

Introduction:-

Nokia is the leader in mobile communication backed by its experience, innovations, user friendliness and secure solutions; the company has become the leading supplier of mobile phones and a leading supplier of mobile, fixed broadband and IP networks. By adding mobility to the internet Nokia creates new opportunities for companies and further enriches the daily lives of people. Nokia is a broadly need company with listing on six major exchanges.

History:-

Nokia was founded in 1865 by Fredrik Idestam in Finland as a paper manufacturing company, in 1920, Finish Rubber works became a part of the company, and later on in 1922, finish cable works joined them. All the three companies were merged in 1967 to form Nokia group.

About Nokia In India:-

Nokia entered the Indian market in 1994. The first ever GMS call in India was made on a Nokia 2110 mobile phone on its own network in 1955. In 2005, Nokia was recognized as the 'Brand of the year 'by the confederation of Indian industry, India's apex industry association. The company was chosen for this award because of its high brand recall, well established distribution channels and being "most preferred" by the consumers.

Besides, Nokia was the market leader in mobile communication devices in India. The company has been carrying out sales and marketing, customer care and research and development activities in the country nokia consider India to be one of its most important markets.

Objective Of The Studies:-

Nokia ,which is the only company in the top 20 brands that is not based in any of the three centuries is a great example of this trend Nokia started operations in India in 1995. In 2005, India is among the top 5 markets for nokia worldwide..Nokia has developed major efforts in adopting its products and advertising to the specificities and tastes in the India market.

Objective of the studies can be explain as follows

- 1) Cellular business is booming in India and it is observed that in 21st century India has became one of the biggest market in mobile sector.
- 2) Cellular service has penetrated the lowest income strata. Few years back the mobile phones ere very few competitive thereby only the high society were using mobile phones. But today the strategy has changed. Their are various competitors and different range of mobile right from Rs.500 to Rs.60,000 and above .So that today even low class people can effort to have mobile phones.
- 3) Standard of living of metros and non metros both growing at fast space. Day by day, villages are becoming to towns, towns to cities and cities are converting to metros.
- 4) Multiple Network connectives have been used by various customers and thereby desire of various range of mobile phone connectivity is increasing day by day.
- 5) Desire of the customers to upgrade their handset is ever-increasing due to speed of advance technology.

Research Methodology:-

Research is like a long journey on the path of finding a new knowledge .the purpose of the research of these topic may be studied as under-

Nokia study finds mobile communication revolutionizing economic and social development in rural India. Mobile communication is revolutionizing economic and social life in rural India , spawning a wave of local entrepreneurs and creating greater access to social services according to a new study by the center for knowledge societies commissioned by nokia.the research identifies seven major services sectors including transport ,finance and healthcare that could be radically transformed through mobile technologies.

There are different companies mobile phones available inspite of it if a consumer think to buy a mobile it's the nokia the branded name because “eye level is buy level “i.e “jo dikhata hai wahi bikta hai.”

If the house of talent is in good health then, there is no limit to ones growth, only sky is the limit class is preferring nokia due to its various range of products.

The Global Hr Picture

When it comes to business, the world is indeed becoming a smaller place. more and more companies are operating across geographic and cultural boundaries .while most have adapted to the global reality in their operations, many are lagging behind in developing the human resource policies,structures,and services that support globalization. The human resource function faces many challenges during the globalization process, including creating a global mind-set within the HR group, creating practices that will be consistently applied in different locations offices while also maintaining the various local cultures and practices and communicating a consistent corporate culture across the entire organization.

To meet these challenges, organization needs to consider the HR function not as just an administrative service but as a strategic business partner. The main focus will be the key to creating a consistent corporate culture across multiple locations in maintaining the critical balance between a strong corporate culture and local cultural difference. There is one major resource which can help to achieve this challenges it is human resource.

Human Resource Management

As organization vary in size, aims, functions, complexity, construction, the physical nature of their product and appeal as employers, so do the contribution of human resource management. The ultimate aim of the function is to “Ensure that at all time the Business is correctly staffed by the right number of people with the skills relevant to the business needs “ i.e neither over staffed nor under staffed in total or in respect of any one discipline or work great.

Internal marketing simply means preparing your employees to Handel every interaction a customer might have with your company. It is also the process of building relationship capital through effective communication with employees. HR professional can play a critical role in helping there organization grow through internal marketing.

People are really what make any company unique. Competitors can replicate product or service offerings, but what they can't replicate are the people who compromise an organization's personality and culture.

HRM in International MKT regarding NOKIA

HRM in the new economy ought to a human contract with a strong technology focus. We need to leverage on emerging technologies to better satisfy the wants and need of the knowledge workers, and in the process, build a competitive advantage that lasts. Attraction and retention of talent have become the main external influence on Nokias human resources strategies, as other companies also strive to be the employee of choice. The HR manager is also challenged with the task of priority the skills ,cultures ,atmosphere and processes necessary for knowledge and capabilities.Nokia believes in the importance of the individual ,whether he or she is an employee ,business partner or customer.

Marketing Strategy Of Nokia Mobile Phone:-

Marketing strategy of a company is a policy to maintain its competitive position in the market. Management gives it a shape with strategies for each controllable of product,

distribution, promotion and pricing. Keeping in view all the marketing strategies of a company the Nokia Company generally gives training to all their marketing executives who help to increase the sales volume and to maintain its competitive position in the market.

Strategic human resources management approach is largely about integration and adaptation, its concern is to ensure that:

- Human resource management is fully integrated with the strategy and the strategic needs of the firm
- HR practices are adjusted, accepted, and used by line managers and employees as part of their everyday work.

Some Major Features Of Hr In Globalization

Creating a global mind-set within the HR group, creating practices that will be consistently applied in different locations/offices while also maintaining the various local cultures and practices and communicating a consistent corporate culture across the entire organization .considering the HR function not as just an administrative service but as a strategies business partner. Companies are involving the human resources department in developing and implementing both business and people strategies by creating a consistent corporate culture:-

- Communicate to all locations about a common corporate culture.
- Allow local cultures to maintain their identity in the context of the corporate culture.
- Establish common systems (e.g accounting,marketing,MIS)
- Provide management with education outlining how the company does business.
- Create an organizational mission with input from all locations.
- Create a written strategy outlining the corporate culture.

Conclusion

Through its subsidiaries the company operates as a global provider of business information and insight about mobile phones with new technologies. The quality process

provides customers with quality business information . This quality information is the foundation on which customer to make critical business dictions. Their business solutions are to help causes convert prospects to consumers faster.

The research study finally revealed that there is a need for improvement and for the some following are suggestions:-

PRODUCT- I believe Nokia already have its product and manufactured a specific quantity based in my research.

PRICE –As we know Nokia entered a very large market with so many competitive in my opinion the only things Nokia have to do is to minimize its prices to reach at least to a large number of Indian poor families because poverty in India is 65% of the total population.

PROMOTION:- a lot of ideas for marketing for product is to get targets and based on it start to enter Nokia market and give free mobiles sometimes when participating in the events or companies events to introduce to product in the proper way.

DISTRIBUTION:- Set channel for distribution that would deliver its products to the areas that are targeted .sometimes even to provide discount or some schema for customer satisfaction /attraction.

I think India is large market with potential but it got to study population more in order to come up with a reasonable strategy. As of today , Nokia has a 70-80 percent market share which is on the rise as

- This is inclusive of GSM and CDMA
- LG has expressed intent to sway, their near monopoly so their handsets are better but the trust of majority of the customers is with Nokia.

General suggestion regarding further research:

The journey of nokia mobile phone is never ending. The more information you get the more has to be yet to come .Each and every effort has been made to get the maximum possible information ,and conducted the research work as scientifically as possible .There areas still various kind of research can further be done.

Challenges that anybody would face in this industry would be the ability to recognize early on the various disruptions that trigger growth. As an organization, you have to be strategizing the various scenarios and think ahead. You have to keep up with innovations to match the changing consumer requirements and social trends. Building capabilities to be able to address the changing needs of consumers is critical. The challenge lies in the ability to attach you from getting pulled along in the scorching pace of growth and to be able to recognize the emerging trends and how to impact and change these emerging trends. Only then you can overcome any challenges that come in the source of success.

Current Affairs :- Microsoft to acquire Nokia's devices & services business

REDMOND, Washington and ESPOO, Finland – Sept. 3, 2013 – Microsoft Corporation and Nokia Corporation today announced that the Boards of Directors for both companies have decided to enter into a transaction whereby Microsoft will purchase substantially all of Nokia's Devices & Services business, license Nokia's patents, and license and use Nokia's mapping services.

Under the terms of the agreement, Microsoft will pay EUR 3.79 billion to purchase substantially all of Nokia's Devices & Services business, and EUR 1.65 billion to license Nokia's patents, for a total transaction price of EUR 5.44 billion in cash. Microsoft will draw upon its overseas cash resources to fund the transaction. The transaction is expected to close in the first quarter of 2014, subject to approval by Nokia's shareholders, regulatory approvals and other closing conditions.

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